

Recommended citation: Zergout, I., Ajana, S., Bakkali, S., & Adam, C. (2019). Systemic approach to address complexity in the training of engineers in innovation and creativity: Modelling the process of implementing innovative projects. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 1296-1306). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14656706.

Systemic approach to address complexity in the training of engineers in innovation and creativity: Modelling process of implementing innovative projects

I. ZERGOUT¹

ENSEM- University of Hassan II
CASABLANCA, MOROCCO

S. AJANA

ENSEM- University of Hassan II
CASABLANCA, MOROCCO

S. BAKKALI

ENSEM- University of Hassan II
CASABLANCA, MOROCCO

C. ADAM

ENSTA Bretagne,
BREST, FRANCE

Conference Key Areas: New Complexity Quest in Engineering Sciences

Keywords: Innovation process, model, PBL, action research

ABSTRACT

Innovation has always been considered as a complex and multidisciplinary phenomenon. The understanding and representation of this complexity has been addressed in several works in the field of management sciences from a systemic approach that clarifies the different components of innovation and defines their interrelationships. In this work, the systemic approach to innovation has been addressed in a different complex context, which is the training of mechanical engineers in innovation and creativity. This concept can be regarded as a process involving the interaction of a set of human and material resources managed in order to develop the skills necessary for innovative projects. The main objective of this work is to test the validity of a systemic modelling of the innovation training process for engineers. To this end, the action-research methodology made it possible to experiment with the model proposed during Project-Based Learning (PBL) activities within an engineering school. The analysis of the results confirmed the hypotheses of the effectiveness of the approach adopted in stimulating innovation among engineering students. This approach divides the main process into sub-processes (the implementation process, the support process, and the management process). The contribution of this study lies in the design of a new method that could be applied by professors and students, and which could improve engineering students'

¹ Corresponding author: zergout.imane@gmail.com, ID: 1682

ability to innovate while ensuring the professionalization and management of innovative projects.

INTRODUCTION

The stimulation of innovation among engineers go hand in hand with the socio-economic development of countries that have oriented their concerns towards together knowledge and innovation based economy, namely Morocco [1]. Indeed, the development and production of major innovative projects in the various socio-economic fields are largely based on the skills of engineers and their capacity to innovate [2].

The ability to innovate is based on a set of skills and knowledge that generate innovative thinking among engineers and future engineers and motivate them to produce something new in the field of their expertise. These skills are not limited to technical ones, but soft skills are also crucial in boosting innovation, in particular; autonomy, proactivity, empowerment, communication, problem solving...etc.[3] These skills are encouraged through active teaching methods such as digital integration, international opening, learning through individual and collective projects, interdisciplinary projects, etc. [4]. Several authors have shown the vital role played by students' projects realised in their schools or during internships in the development of innovation and creativity in students [5] [6] [7]. Project based learning (PBL) involves a set of actors in real situations, including future engineers, which allows them to follow the different technical and analytical steps (understanding, analysis, solution proposal, evaluation...etc.) to solve complex problems located in socio-technical contexts. This type of learning leads students to reflect deeply while taking into account all the characteristics and issues of the project's scope (social, cultural, economic, political, technological...) [8]. Nevertheless, the solutions proposed by future engineers to solve problems related to their fields are still standard solutions and do not demonstrate a big deal of creativity and innovation [9]. This is mainly the result of a lack of precise models of the organization of the means, resources and methods deployed to boost students' ability to innovate within engineering training institutions [4]. In an attempt to address these problems, we have conducted researches aiming at understanding and improving the process of training engineers in innovation through PBL. This issue deals with a subject considered complex since it aims to design a systemic model that represents the complexity of the innovation training process and integrates a set of material and human resources. A complex system consists of a set of varied elements characterized by autonomy, freedom and interaction with its environment [10] [11]. In this work, complexity is perceptible through different aspects: the complexity of engineering training, which is in dynamic interaction with its environment (industry, research centres, etc.), the complexity of the innovation phenomenon, and the complexity of adopting a modelling approach for a set of human practices and behaviours in the form of processes. In an initiative to

understand the complexity of the system under study, we have proceeded through a systemic approach based on models, methods, and technical tools.

The objective of this article is to test the validity of a proposed innovation process model that could be implemented in projects realized by mechanical engineering students in an engineering school in Morocco. This model has already been designed in previous work based on theoretical data and an empirical study. Our systemic modelling of innovation process aims to represent and organise skills, knowledge and resources in innovation projects in a logical and interactive way. We begin by presenting the methodology, the proposed model and the working hypotheses. Then we describe the details of the different experiments of the model such as the context, objectives and results obtained for each case studied. We conclude with the contribution and perspectives of the study.

1 METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

This work is carried out according to a qualitative approach based on the action research method that we have conducted within the Mechanical Engineering Department at the High National School of Electricity and Mechanics (ENSEM) in Casablanca, as a researcher and teacher. This approach allows a return between practice and theory, and highlights the direct involvement of the researcher in the action. The tools used in our method are active and participatory observation, which results from the researcher's integration into the study, as well as actual intervention and evaluation of results [12]. This method allowed a cycle of experiments to be carried out to put into practice and test the validity of our proposed model on the one hand, and to demonstrate the relevance of the systemic approach to understand a complex system, on the other.

2 SYSTEMIC MODELLING OF THE INNOVATION PROCESS IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION

Systemic modelling consists in understanding a complex phenomenon through the development of a graphical and intelligible representation that makes it possible to represent it and to predict the results of possible interactions between this phenomenon and the components of its environment [11]. There are various methods and tools available to develop a systemic model. In our case, we have adopted the process approach which is considered as a systemic approach characterized by the study of several levels of analysis [13]. It consists of a methodical and detailed description of an organisation or activity generating added value in order to control and continuously improve it by acting on the interactions between the process and its environment². Innovation training can be considered as a process because it consists of a set of sequentially linked steps aimed at transforming engineering students into innovative engineers in order to meet the needs and requirements expressed by different organisations in the socio-economic

² <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/fr/>

world. The process approach divides the system studied into three main sub-processes interacting and exchanging a flow of information and resources: the implementation process, the support process, and the management process [13]. It's important to mention that this model represents a nonlinear process, because there are interactions among the different components of the process, and the different phases of the process could not respect the order proposed in this model. That

means that we can start a new phase without completing the last one, or we can return to change some details in another past phase.

Fig. 1. The proposed systemic model of the innovation process in students projects

The proposed model in figure 1 and detailed in table 1 allowed us to identify steps and guidelines to be implemented when supervising projects carried out by engineering students so that they are innovative and creative.

Table 1: the components of the process for the implementation and support of innovative mechanical engineering projects

Stages of the implementation process		Elements of the support process		
		Means	Methods	Actors
Creativity	Define and analyse a problem	Control charts, metrology tools, questionnaires, calculation and statistics software,...etc.	Active observation, experimental design, statistical control of processes,...etc.	Any person concerned by the problem, supervisors
	Generate creative ideas	Internet, scientific databases, sites concerned by technology,...etc.	Technology watch, brainstorming,...etc.	Supervisors, PhD students
	Evaluate and choose a solution	Calculation software,...etc.	Decision-making methods, benchmarking,...etc.	Supervisors, PhD students
Feasibility study	Listening to the needs of different stakeholders	Questionnaire, social networks, applications for studying audiences and market news,...etc.	Market research, customer orientation, design thinking,...etc.	Project clients, supervisors, engineers
	Study of the	Project management software (MSProject),	Project management, finance, risk	Engineers, supervisors,

	technical and financial feasibility	calculation software (Excel),...etc.	management	accountants
	Define the business plan	Project portfolio	Innovation management tools	Engineers (project managers or contractors)
Development	Define the functional specifications	Standard NF X 50-100	Functional analysis, Value analysis...etc.	Supervisors, engineers, doctoral students
	Design and dimension	Computer-aided design and drawing and mechanical calculation software (Catia, Abaqus, Autocad...etc.)	Calculation of structures	PhD students, R&D engineers, supervisors
	Test and validate (make a prototype)	Manufacturing machines, 3D printer, Metrology tools, three-dimensional metrology machine, computer-aided design and manufacturing software, mechanical testing and non-destructive testing machines, raw material, miscellaneous equipment	sizing, design and technical drawing, eco-design	Technicians, supervisors, mechanical production engineers, ...etc.
Realize	Search for ways and means	Quotation, sponsorship file, contact database	Mechanical engineering techniques, manufacturing process of materials...etc.	Customers, sponsors
	Realize and implement	Manufacturing machines, 3D printer, Metrology tools, three-dimensional metrology machine, computer-aided design and manufacturing software, mechanical testing and non-destructive testing machines, raw material, miscellaneous equipment	Negotiation and communication skills, marketing	Technicians, supervisors, mechanical production engineers, ...etc.
Diffuse	Evaluate	PPT, prototype, implementation results....	Mechanical engineering techniques, manufacturing process of materials...etc.	Professors and industrialists
	Diffuser	Poster, Packaging, Social Networks	Evaluation criteria	Customers

This model was built on the basis of data from the literature review on the one hand, and a set of empirical studies on the other. In our work, we focused only on progressive innovation, because it was difficult to achieve radical innovations requiring more advanced resources and considerable time [14]. In order to prove the

validity of our proposal, we formulated hypotheses based on the model, which we verified through experiments. The hypotheses of our study are as follows:

H1: The respect of the steps of the proposed implementation process improves the ability of engineering students to produce innovative solutions.

H2: A support process involving the interaction of different means, methods and actors in connection with each step of the implementation process improves the ability of engineering students to produce innovative solutions.

H3: A management process controlling the level of skill acquisition at each step of the process improves the ability of engineering students to innovate.

3 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE MODEL

3.1 Pedagogical experimentation 1: Case of graduation projects

3.1.1 Context and objectives of the study

The objective of this experimentation is to produce innovative solutions for graduation projects dealing with complex industrial issues by following the stages of the proposed innovation process and the elements that characterize it. This experiment made it possible to test the effect of the respect of the implementation process, as well as the use of technical and material methods and means on the ability of engineering students to innovate.

3.1.2 Procedure of the experiment

The sample consists of ten graduation projects carried out by students from the last year of mechanical engineering at ENSEM in different industrial companies acting in the following fields (Energy production, food-processing industry, automotive industry, Aeronautic industry, and Phosphate industry). These projects belong to different domains of mechanical engineering such as: mechanical system design, quality management, and mechanical maintenance.

We participated in the supervision of five of these projects with the academic and industrial supervisors. During this experiment, we ensured that the steps of the proposed process were applied and that its components were respected. The remaining five projects are considered as demonstration projects, which were carried out under equivalent conditions in order to compare results. It is important to note that the demonstration projects and the projects concerned by the study took place in similar conditions (study programme, company where the internship takes place, students' courses, supervising professors belonging to the same mechanical engineering department), the only different element is the approach to supervision and implementation of the project.

These graduation projects last 4 months. Weekly meetings are held between academic supervisors (our team) and engineering students. On the other side, students meet approximately every day with their industrial supervisor in the company hosting the project.

In the first phase of the project, we focused on the creativity and the generation of innovative ideas. After having carried out an inventory and an analytical study of the various problems in the field, the engineering students are led to use tools from the creative problem-solving process to generate innovative ideas. Then decision-making methods are used to choose the most appropriate solution. Then, we have carried out a preliminary study of the technical and financial feasibility of this solution in order to define the business plan and verify the applicability of the project. The next phase consists of the technical study of the project, where the engineering students applied the various technical knowledge they acquired during the training years, including design, dimensioning, technical drawing and calculation methods. In the last phase, students were required to seek funding and equipment to implement their solutions. Finally, the diffusion of project results can take different forms: first, the presentation of the project report to the managers of the company where the internship took place. Secondly a presentation of the project in the school to a jury composed of professors and industrial actors who will assess the results. If the result of the innovation process is a new product, the latter could be marketed by the company itself or by another means. During the whole project, engineering students are invited to interact with different actors within the company (technicians, administrators, engineers...), and within their school (doctoral students, professors...) by asking for their advice and contribution to make their projects a success.

3.1.3 Project assessment and analysis

A jury composed of professors and industrial actors first assessed the innovative aspect of the various solutions proposed through every project on the basis of the innovation criteria of the OMPIC (Moroccan Office of Industrial and Commercial Property), which is the Moroccan organisation responsible for granting the following patents³ : novelty and creativity, added value, industrial applicability. Then, the jury noted the level of respect of each project of the different components of the innovation process presented in Table 1. This rating is based on the following Likert scale (1: not respected; 2: poorly respected; 3: respected; 4: much respected. Then we calculated the average respect obtained by all the supervised and the demonstration project for the different components and stages of the innovation process. The table below summarizes the results obtained.

Table 2. Analysis of the impact of the support process on projects

Phases	Creativity			Feasibility study			Development			Realization			Diffusion			N
	Methods	Means	Stages	Methods	Means	Stages	Methods	Means	Stages	Methods	Means	Stages	Methods	Means	Stages	
Supervised projects	3,33	2,67	3,33	3,00	2,67	3,00	3,33	2,67	3,67	2,67	2,33	2,33	2,00	1,67	2,00	5
Demonstration project	1,67	1,33	2,00	2,33	1,00	1,33	3,00	1,33	3,67	1,67	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,33	1

³ <http://www.ompic.org.ma/fr/content/propos-du-brevet-dinvention>

N: number of innovative solutions proposed

We clearly observe that the five projects that we have supervised based on the proposed approach have a more innovative aspect compared to the five pilot projects that followed a traditional supervision following a technical approach. According to the averages obtained, 60% of the supervised projects respected the stages of the innovation process. These projects respected 60% of the means proposed by the process and 80% of the methods proposed. This allows us to confirm hypothesis H1 and H2.

3.2 Pedagogical experiment 2: case of projects carried out during a course

3.2.1 Context and objectives of the study

The objective of this experiment is to work on innovation projects in parallel with a course on environmental and sustainable development management. We focused in this experiment mainly on the level of skills' acquisition needed to innovate and their impact on the production of creative and innovative solutions by students. These last include technical and soft skills detailed in the table 3. Technical skills are derived from the syllabus and objectives of this course as well as other courses that assist in the realization of projects (product design, problem solving, technical drawing...), obtained from internal accreditation documents. As for transversal skills, we have identified the common ones among skill models necessary for innovation developed by some authors [2] [4] [8].

3.2.2 Procedure of the experiment

Our sample consists of a class of 24 mechanical engineering students. This course lasts 1 month and consists of 6 sessions. The first two sessions were devoted to the theoretical concepts of the course. Then, we devoted two sessions to the first three steps of the process: creativity, idea generation and development. Unfortunately, we were unable to continue the rest of the process due to lack of time and financial resources. A final session was dedicated to the evaluation and presentation of project results. These sessions were in the form of workshops in which we participated in supervision alongside the course's teacher. During these workshops, students formed teams of 4 people, and worked on solving technical problems related to the respect of environmental standards in different areas of their school (dormitories, spaces for mechanical workshops and practical work, classrooms...) by proposing innovative solutions. The conduct and supervision of the workshops were similar to Experiment 1, and we ensured the implementation of active teaching methods and the integration of digital technology to help students acquire the skills necessary for innovation.

3.2.3 Projects assessment and analysis

The results of projects are evaluated by a jury composed of the professor and doctoral engineering students based on the innovation criteria of Experiment 1: novelty, added value and industrial applicability. We invited the jury to analyse the

reports and the presentation of the studied projects, and to note the response of these deliverables to certain criteria related to some aptitudes that could contribute to the acquisition of the skills needed to boost innovation. The rating is based on the following Likert scale (1: no Satisfactory, 2: poorly satisfactory, 3: satisfactory, 4: very satisfactory). The results of the evaluation are presented in the table 3. Then we calculated the average of satisfaction to all the required skills and we studied the correlation with the innovativeness of the project.

Table 3. Analysis of the relationship between innovation skills and innovative projects.

Projects	NOTES												Average	Innovativeness of the project	
	Soft skills						Technical skills								
	Analytical thinking	Risk taking	Interprofessional communication	Creative problem solving.	Systematic analysis	Ability to adapt	Define and analyse a problem	Use ICTs	Define a business plan	Define a functional specification	Map a process	Design and dimension			Use of specific tools for innovative problem
Intelligent water recovery system	4	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	2	4	3	4	3.53	Positive
Sorting of waste using a "Smart Bin"	4	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	2	2	4	4	4	3.46	Positive
Recycling of mechanical parts	3	2	4	3	2	4	4	1	2	2	4	3	4	3	Positive
Design of an intelligent dust misting system	4	2	4	4	3	4	4	1	2	2	4	3	4	3	Positive
Change management using ICT	3	2	4	2	1	2	4	1	2	1	4	2	4	2.46	Negative
Intelligent green space watering system	1	2	3	1	1	2	3	1	2	1	4	2	4	2	Negative

The results show that the ability to produce innovative solutions increases with the rise of the acquisition level of the various skills required for innovation by students. This leads us to the confirmation of the hypothesis H3 of the study.

4 CONCLUSION

This article aims at validating an educational system proposed through our research study in order to understand and represent the complexity of engineering innovation training. We tested the validity of a systemic modelling likely to boost innovation in future engineers. We have carried out two experiments to show the positive impact of the interaction between diversified resources (resources, methods, actors) and the management of the skills needed for innovation, in strengthening the capacity to produce innovative and creative solutions in complex industrial and academic contexts.

The contribution of this work is to shed light on the importance of developing an interdisciplinary approach in which the theoretical notions call for complementary scientific disciplines (engineering, management and educational sciences) to understand what's at the core of innovation in engineering education. As perspective, we aim to extend our experiments through the application of the proposed model to a set of projects carried out within the other departments of the ENSEM (electrical, industrial and computer engineering) in order to ensure continuous improvement of our process.

References

- [1] Djeflat, A, (2012), Les efforts du Maroc dans l'économie fondée sur la connaissance, CMI, Marseille.
- [2] Kövesi, K, and Csizmadia P, (2018), Formation des ingénieurs à l'innovation, Iste editions, London, pp.76-87.
- [3] Besançon, M, Lubart T and Barbot B, (2013), Creative Giftedness and Educational Opportunities, Educational and Child Psychology, vol.30, n°2, pp.79-88.
- [4] Cardona Gil, E, Gardelle L, and Tabas B, (2018), Formation des ingénieurs à l'innovation, Iste editions, London, pp.26.
- [5] Soares, F O, Sepúlveda M J, Monteiro S, Lima R M and Dinis-Carvalho J, (2013), An integrated project of entrepreneurship and innovation in engineering education, Mechatronics, vol.23, pp.987–996.
- [6] Kojmane, J, and Aboutajeddine A, (2015), Enjoyeering Senior: Un projet de conception et développement de produits innovants pour les élèves-ingénieurs, Xème Conférence Internationale : Conception et Production Intégrées, Tangier, Morocco.
- [7] Silva, A, Leite M, Vilas-Boas J and Simões R, (2018), How education background affects design outcome: teaching product development to mechanical engineers, industrial designers and managers, European Journal of Engineering Education.
- [8] Adam, C, and Coco S, (2018), Formation des ingénieurs à l'innovation, Iste editions, London, pp.239-243.
- [9] Forest, J, Chouteau M and Nguyen C, (2011), Conceptions de l'innovation et formations de l'ingénieur, Les cahiers du Musée des confluences : Innovation, vol.7, pp.37-47.
- [10] De Rosnay, J, (1975), Le Macroscopie. Vers une vision globale, Editions du Seuil, Paris.
- [11] Le Moigne, J-L, (1990-1995), La modélisation des systèmes complexes, Dunod, Paris.
- [12] Cohen, L, Manion L and Morrison K, (2007), Research methods in education, Routledge, London, pp. 228.

[13] Brandenburg, H, and Wojtyna J-P, (2006), Approche processus mode d'emploi, Editions d'Organisations, Paris.

[14] Tiphaine Liu, T, (2015), Innovation cyclique ou radicale : le choix des écoles d'ingénieur, Les actes du Colloque INGENIUM "Création-créativité et innovation dans la formation et l'activité d'ingénieur", Paris, France.